

Beyond “Authenticities”? Preliminary Thoughts on Epistemologies of Early Music¹

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Abstract. When browsing through performers’ websites and advertisements for recordings, early instruments, and concerts, one cannot but conclude that “authenticity” seems to still play a major role in self-definitions and marketing concepts of the “movement” of historically informed performance practice. Having already been deprived of its claims to originality in the 1980s, and meanwhile, being part of the same academic establishment, it battled in its early days, historically informed performance practice needed to reposition itself in terms of its similarities and particularities when compared to artistic research during the last decades. Since experimentation was one of its characterizing features in terms of repertoire, instrument building, and playing techniques, and since audience experience was a central issue from the very beginning, there seems to be much common ground with artistic research, even “avant la lettre”. But these similarities are consistently minimized by HIP promoters’ need for an othering self-definition: in many cases they seem to directly or implicitly adhere to their claims of authenticity and originality, even when speaking about situated or embodied knowledge. This paper explores the common ground of HIP and various approaches to artistic research. It reflects on the methodic paths that opened historical thinking for artistic approaches and which could likewise open HIP for establishing characteristic features beyond claims of being “authentic.”

The areas of overlap between historical music research and systematic methodologies of the field, which have become increasingly evident in the academic landscape during the last decades, have of course had fundamental theoretical and practice-related consequences for so-called historically informed performance practice. Resulting from an outspokenly hybrid position between different methodologies of research, between theory and practice, between institutionalization and claims of an academic subculture, between the past of the time of creation and the present of performance, as well as between internalization and performance to the outside as a mode of communication, very different assessments of and opinions on a new status of the field come to light. This is due to the many points of view on the subject matter and related intentions of the manifold participants. Even the naming (and thereby also definition) of this field of musical performance and research itself is nowadays marked by a certain perplexity.

This essay traces the lines of discussion of one aspect of this broadly controversial field, which is centered around claims and content of the concept of “authenticity.” This is for two reasons: on the one hand, the term is used in a redundant way in numerous definitions from within and outside of the field; on the other hand, it builds a bridge to empirical

1. I would like to thank Yannick Wey and Marc-Antoine Camp for their editing work and Nathalie Kirschstein for her linguistic revision of the essay.

methodologies. I concentrate on the (mis)use and meaning of “authenticity” in culturally derived performance practice² from the perspective of a (white, university-educated, Western European) music historian with curatorial experience and competences in empirical methods, who has explored and experienced the broad practical implications of the field from project collaborations with musicians. From this point of view, what follows will be less about analyzing practical approaches to particular musical artifacts than about selectively summarizing the issues that have emerged in recent literature and asking about their theoretical, aesthetic, and philosophical starting points and possible consequences. It thus follows argumentation methods of the rationalist rather than the empiricist side of the epistemological spectrum.

Mapping the ground in between

Two particularly telling and seemingly contradictory excerpts from research literature that map the field of tension in which my essay operates are prefaced here. One of these passages is by Michelle Dulak and was published in 1993. From my point of view, it has proven to be accurate and also purposeful for the discussion of current questions that constitute the field of research today:

How shall we speak of the ‘early-music movement’? We lack a satisfactory name for the phenomenon today; none of the old solutions seem right any more. ‘Early music’ itself will hardly do, when so much of the repertoire concerned is so recent. (If even Brahms is now to be considered ‘early,’ surely we have exhausted the word’s usefulness.) ‘Authentic’ has succumbed to a thousand critical blows, most of them richly deserved. ‘Contextual,’ for no very obvious reason, was stillborn [...] Perhaps the strain of determining which contexts counted did it in. ‘Period’ and ‘historical’ (with the variant ‘historically informed’) remain, but a careful observer cannot help noting that even they become even rarer with time; we are resorting instead to complex circumlocutions.³

The other quotation is a remark by Richard Taruskin from his groundbreaking study on historicism in performance first published in 1988, and also quoted by Dulak, which from my perspective has been overtaken in the ongoing discussions on early music and its so-called HIP movement during the last decades:

Yet the ideal of authenticistic performance grew up alongside modernism, shares its tenets, and will probably decline alongside it as well. Its values, its

2. On the conceptualization of the term “culturally derived performance practice” and on terminology in this field in general, cf. Harer, I. (2001). “Alte Musik” – “Aufführungspraxis” – “Authentizität”: Tendenzen bei der Neudefinition der Begriffe im anglo-amerikanischen Sprachraum. In J. Trummer (Ed.), *Bach im Mittelpunkt – Botschaften an die Aufführungspraxis* (pp.67-80). Con Brio. See also Dulak’s reference to the term, below, fn. 2.

3. Dulak, M. (1993). The Quiet Metamorphosis of “Early Music”. *Repercussions*, 2(2), 31-61, here 31. <https://www.ocf.berkeley.edu/~repercus/repercussions-fall-1993-vol-2-no-2>.

justification, and, yes, its authenticity, will only be revealed in conjunction with those of modernism.⁴

Since the theoretical deconstruction of authenticity in early music performance, neither the diverse movement itself, whose market forces have developed since, nor the use of “authenticity” as one of its distinguishing criteria has disappeared. That there are still no accepted alternative terms to “correctly” capture the characteristics and aims of the early music movements and their ever broadening range of musical fields, makes setting out to explore the current theoretical ground in between these two quotes a promising approach.

“Authenticities” prevailing explicitly

Browsing through websites or concert advertisements and critiques, or even through more recent essays and book publications of “historically informed” artists and/or researchers, it is impossible not to be confronted with claims of “authenticity” without quotation marks and in a reinforcing sense⁵: concerts are praised to be or have been “authentic” (see e.g. the concert review “Authentisch und leidenschaftlich: Ein perfekt gepudertes Barockabend”⁶) and web advertisements for an early music-festival use the term (“Exemplarisch. Authentisch. Begeisternd. Einfach gute Musik!”⁷). Instruments on which to play are said to have this quality (see the question “Wie authentisch kann der Nachbau eines Holzblasinstruments überhaupt sein? Ist eher die Kopie eines bestimmten Instruments oder eine Kopie seines Klangs anzustreben?”⁸). The term even appears in some recent essays and research publications on the subject of early music, sometimes in the plural, but not fundamentally questioned (see, for example, the title of a study in *Early Music America* “Authentic Baroque Performance is Energizing Young Performers,”⁹ a recent study on René Jacobs “Authentisch nach dem Buchstaben – authentisch nach dem Sinn. Über Alte Musik

4. Taruskin, R. (1995). The Pastness of the Present and the Presence of the Past. In R. Taruskin, *Text and Act. Essays on Music and Performance* (pp. 90-154, here position 1335-1336 (kindle)). Oxford University Press. (Reprinted from *Authenticity and Early Music*, pp.137-207, by N. Kenyon (Ed.), 1988, Oxford University Press).

5. On the importance of the concept in advertisement see Müller, K. H. (2013). *Wiederentdeckung und Protest. Alte Musik im kulturellen Gedächtnis* (pp.167-178). Königshausen & Neumann.

6. Zentralplus. (posted 2018, April 16; last accessed 2021, July 29). *Authentisch und leidenschaftlich: Ein perfekt gepudertes Barockabend*. <https://www.zentralplus.ch/authentisch-und-leidenschaftlich-ein-perfekt-gepudertes-barockabend-830853/>.

7. Heinrich Schütz Musikfest (2021, October; last accessed 2021, July 29). “vnter den fürnembsten Musicis” 7.-17. Oktober 2021. <http://www.schuetz-musikfest.de>.

8. HKB Forschung (posted 2012, February; last accessed 2021, July 29). *Le Basson Savary*. <https://www.hkb-interpretation.ch/projekte/basson-savary/article-29>.

9. *Early Music America*. (posted 2017, September 10; last accessed 2021, July 29). *Authentic Baroque Performance is Energizing Young Performers*. <https://www.earlymusicamerica.org/web-articles/authentic-baroque-performance-is-energizing-young-performers/>.

und historische Aufführungspraxis,”¹⁰ or on “Early Music in the Modern Age,” a study which is praised to have “A groundbreaking dialectical position on ‘authenticity’”¹¹).

“Authenticity” or “authenticities” prevail. This is remarkable since with the very word the assumption of a researcher making findings about how music sounded, or was played or performed back then, and leaving the practitioner (and maybe the same person) “only” the part of executing what she – or more often, he – found out, is implicitly replicated. Authenticity and its plural are still magic terms of early music, although German speaking theorists and musicologists already lined out the doubtfulness of the concept when applied to performance during the 1950s and 1960s¹² and Richard Taruskin traced its roots in modernity during the late 1980,¹³ causing controversial and far-reaching theoretical discussions.¹⁴ These discussions, however, by no means led to a banishment of the word from the early music vocabulary, but rather to its redefinition or pluralization.¹⁵ The question therefore seems not to be so much if authenticity, when applied to performance, is a theoretically doubtful concept, but much more how we deal with that as a form of theoretical and obviously academically situated knowledge.

“Authenticities” prevailing implicitly

Focusing on and underlining that point, Eitan Ornoy published an empirical analysis of performers’ attitudes towards these issues in 2006, concluding that traditionalism in regards to the possibilities of “authentic performances” prevails in inner attitudes as well as in artistic practices in the different facets of the early music movements.¹⁶ But it is a most tricky business to deplore that in-depth reception of new research findings so seldomly appears on the concert stages – paradoxically this replicates the core of the authenticity

10. Jacobs, R. & Leopold, S. (2013). *René Jacobs im Gespräch mit Silke Leopold. “Ich will Musik neu erzählen”* (p. 56). Bärenreiter.

11. Wilson, N. (2014). *The Art of Re-enchantment. Making Early Music in the Modern Age*. Oxford University Press, see ad at <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/the-art-of-re-enchantment-9780199939930?cc=ch&lang=en&> (last accessed 2021, July 29) and positions 1439-1886 (kindle) for the chapter “A Tale of Two Authenticities”.

12. See e.g. Fabian, D. (2001). The Meaning of Authenticity and the Early Music Movement – a Historical Review. *International Review of Aesthetics and Sociology of Music*, 32(2), 153-167.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1562264>.

13. Taruskin (1995).

14. See e.g. leHuray, P. (1990). *Authenticity in Performance. Eighteenth-Century Case Studies*. Cambridge University Press. Kivy, P. (1995). *Authenticities. Philosophical Reflections on Musical Performance*. Cornell University Press. Butt, J. (2002). *Playing with History. The Historical Approach to Musical Performance*.

Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511613555> Haynes, B. (2007). *The End of Early Music: A Period Performer’s History of Music for the Twenty-First Century*. Oxford University Press. DOI:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195189872.001.0001 Müller, K. H. (2013).

DOI:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195189872.001.0001 Müller, K. H. (2013).

15. On more outspoken criticism of the term, see Taruskin, R. (1984), “The Authenticity Movement can become a Positivistic Purgatory, Literalistic and Dehumanizing.” *Early Music*, 12(1), 3-12. Following up his arguments, what Taruskin strives for is not so much a matter of avoiding “authenticity,” but defining it the right way, p. 3: “Authenticity [...] is knowing what you mean and whence comes this knowledge. And more than that, even, authenticity is knowing what you are, and acting in accordance with that knowledge.”

16. Ornoy, E. (2006). Between Theory and Practice: Comparative Study of Early Music Performances. *Early Music* 34(2), 233-247. Retrieved August 3, 2021, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3805843>.

concept and its researcher/performer-divide as described above, while criticizing its traditionalism.

Another implicit symptom of adherence to authenticity within early music can be detected with the request for not letting performers influence each other, but the need for each musician to go back to the sources and develop his or her own “authentic” attitude towards the original musical document – be that score, picture, or text.¹⁷ Recordings of colleagues are considered sources of a lesser degree, not simply other ways of approaching historical music repertoire, compared to the visual and written sources stemming “directly” from the time and place in question. This approach also leaves out the increasingly important work with historical sound recordings and their analysis,¹⁸ which also makes it possible to write histories of performance practices – which in turn can have a conscious impact on contemporary practice.

Even nowadays, in times when practice-led research or research-led practice is of utmost concern in the research departments of music universities, it seems that the notion of “authenticity” – whether explicitly or implicitly – remains conceptually embedded in early music. Most interestingly this happens not only along the lines of demarcation between research and practice and their respective epistemologies. Although the role of historical musicology as defining a right or wrong often outside and before practical considerations seems to be overcome in the way that other methodologies are applied, the relation between research and practice often seems to still adhere to the tradition of explorer and executor with clearly distinguished roles.

To deal with the vagaries of the no longer appropriate application of authenticity in the early music movements necessitates thinking outside the box and from entirely different positions. This requires – ideally – all those involved in the research and performance process, with their different competences and training and with often contradictory or conflicting findings, to be open to the comprehensive concerns of dealing with the different layers of time and space that relate to each other in the performance of historical musical repertoires.

The remainder of this essay elaborates some theoretical points of reference on which such an undertaking can be based. Referring to recent developments, two points in particular are of special interest:

a) The relationship between original and copy, already rethought by Walter Benjamin,¹⁹ has been fundamentally redefined in recent developments, among them the so-called New

17. See e.g. <https://www.earlymusicresources.com/Sources-database> or podcasts at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WcQJeMWzvlk>, <https://www.earlymusic.eu/rema-podcast/>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ekidQddlNY>.

18. See e.g. Cook, N. (2010). “The Ghost in the Machine: Towards a Musicology of Recordings.” *Musicae Scientiae*, 34(2), 3-21. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F102986491001400201>

19. Benjamin, W. Das Kunstwerk im Zeitalter seiner technischen Reproduzierbarkeit (1936). In R. Tiedemann & H. Schweppenhäuser (Eds.). (1985). *Walter Benjamin: Gesammelte Schriften* (Vol. 7.1, 350-384). Suhrkamp.

Discipline (Jennifer Walshe)²⁰ and copying techniques originating in popular music,²¹ not least against the background of new digital possibilities of sampling.²²

b) In connection with this, the relationship between the layers of time in the performative moment is redefined as well, and with it the “presence” of history and historical sound. Recent “metahistorical” curatorial practices²³ reflect this aspect as well as new concepts of definition of presences in history.²⁴

Since early music seems to lose its unique selling point within a valid concept of authenticity if the term is abandoned, adherence to this distinction criterion is the logical consequence, not least in order to maintain market power. Even when transferred to music of later epochs and other genres, the guiding principle of culturally derived performance practice always seems to be the question of the intention of “the composer” and a correspondence with performance sounds of his/her time. With this longing for the “authentic,” we may find ourselves right in the center of the nostalgias and retromanias of our time,²⁵ which favor adherence to the – stylized – old over the opportunities of the new. But perhaps the unique feature of culturally derived performance practice, if it needs one, lies precisely within the new, in understanding this music with redefined epistemologies, through the body of the performing artist and with recipients as part of the performative artistic act.

Subculture as meeting point

Far be it from me to want to explain culturally derived performance practice through artistic research alone – a concept unstable and contradictory in itself.²⁶ What both approaches may have in common, however, is their “queer” seat in relation to established academic knowledge, while at the same time already being integrated into the academic enterprise (although not yet fully into all funding programs). Performances of both practices, properly

Rippl, G. & Stolz, M (2019). Original und Kopie: Techniken und Ästhetiken der re/produktiven Abweichung. Sondernummer der *Kulturwissenschaftlichen Zeitschrift*. 4(3). <https://sciendo.com/issue/KWG/4/3>

20. Kloos, F. (2017). *Jennifer Walshe. Spiel mit Identitäten*. Wolke Verlag. Gunkel, D. J. (2016). *Of Remixology. Ethics and Aesthetics after Remix*. MIT Press.

21. Navas, E. & Gallagher, O. & Burrough, X. (Eds.) *The Routledge Companion to Remix Studies* 2017 Routledge; Borschke, M. (2017). *This is not a Remix: Piracy, Authenticity and Popular Music*. Bloomsbury. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5040/9781501318955>

22. Salagean, E. (2008). *Sampling im deutschen, schweizerischen und US-amerikanischen Urheberrecht*. Nomos. Fischer, G. (2020). *Sampling in der Musikproduktion. Das Spannungsfeld zwischen Urheberrecht und Kreativität*. Böhner. DOI 10.14631/978-3-96317-721-7

23. See e.g. Wittocx, E., Demeester, A. Carpreau, P., Bühler, M. & Karskens, X. (Eds.). (2021). *The Transhistorical Museum – Mapping the Field*. Valiz.

24. See e.g. Patel, K. K. (2021). Anwesenheit in der Geschichte. Ein Problemaufriss. Festvortrag zum 30-jährigen Bestehen der Österreichischen Zeitschrift für Geschichtswissenschaften. unter <https://journals.univie.ac.at/index.php/oezg/announcement/view/63>.

25. Reynolds, S. (2012). *Retromania. Pop Culture's Addiction to its Own Past*. Faber and Faber. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1533-1598.2012.01328.x>; Cassin, B. (2021). *Nostalgie. Wann sind wir wirklich zuhause?*. Suhrkamp. Boym, S. (2001). *Future of Nostalgia*. Basic Books.

26. Roesner, D. (2015). Practice-as-Research. Paradox mit Potential. In A.-S. Jürgens & T. Tesche (Eds.) *LaborARTorium. Forschung im Denkraum zwischen Wissenschaft und Kunst. Eine Methodenreflexion* (pp. 25-32). transcript. <https://doi.org/10.14361/9783839429693>

placed and framed, can thus become interventions that question precisely these academic – or even general social – commitments.

In its early days and in the minds of many of its members until today, as Haskell²⁷ and more recently also Müller²⁸ have described in length, early music was meant to be a practice of opposing academic forms of music making, namely the 19th century conservatoire tradition. HIP's steady demand of experimenting with sources in performance lead to a self-definition of subculture. I think when practice-lead researchers today claim that they long for an "Art-induced experience of possible [historical] world conditions,"²⁹ they are arguing very much along the lines of the movement called HIP in its earlier days – although the methods of reflecting and gaining knowledge might not have been exactly the same.

Following a path departing from this point might lead to other forms of overcoming claims of "authenticity" than those already suggested: the multiple possible authenticities in performance which Kivy³⁰ described, or the synchronic diversity of performance options and situations of the same repertoire at the same point of time put forward by Kenny,³¹ or speaking about "authentic" possibilities for performance like Eyndhoven suggested.³² All these approaches still adhere to a notion of belief in originality, even if it is a manifold and unreachable one.

The subversive potential of speaking about the movements formerly called "historically informed" is, today, not so much to hint at the quite obvious overlaps with concepts of embodied knowledge as artistic research *avant la lettre*,³³ but in denying the possibility of any form of "authenticity" in these practices. But how do we operate "beyond authenticities" in early music?

27. Haskell, H. (1988). *The Early Music Revival. A History*. Thames and Hudson.

28. Müller, K. H. (2013).

29. Dubach, S., Badura, J. (2015). Denken/Reflektieren (im Medium der Kunst). In J. Badura, Selma Dubach, Anke Haarmann, Dieter Mersch, Anton Rey, Christoph Schenker & Germán Toro Pérez. *Künstlerische Forschung. Ein Handbuch*. (pp. 123-126, here 124). Diaphanes. <https://diaphanes.net/buch/detail/2385>. "Es (Wissen) manifestiert sich im Prozess des Vollzugs künstlerischer Praxis als 'Agens' eines im Tun aufgehobenen denkenden Forschungsprozesses, [sic!] und generiert kunstinduzierte Erfahrbarkeit möglicher (historischer) Weltverhältnisse."

30. Kivy, P. (1995). *Authenticities. Philosophical Reflections on Musical Performance*. Cornell University Press. Authentic Possibilities

31. Kenny, E. (2008). "The Uses of Lute Song: Texts, Contexts and Pretexts for 'Historically Informed' Performance." *Early Music*, 36(2), 285-299. <https://doi.org/10.1093/em/can045>.

32. Eyndhoven, C. v. (2015). "Mechanical Carillons as a Source for Historical Performance: An Artistic Reconstruction of Seventeenth-Century Carillon Music Using Historical Re-Pinning Books." *Journal of the Alamire Foundation*, 7(1), 103-121. <https://doi.org/10.1484/J.JAF.5.103807>.

33. Vaes, L. (2017). "Artistic Research *Avant la lettre*? The Case of Glenn Gould's Brahms Concerto Interpretation." In J. Impett (Ed.). *Artistic Research in Music: Discipline and Resistance. Artists and Researchers at the Orpheus Institute*. (pp. 108-133). Leuven University Press. <https://muse.jhu.edu/book/57955>.

Metadiscourses

In order to find that out, it can be most helpful to treat the debates about early music as objects of research themselves. We need discursive analyses as a way to understand which protagonists shape the discourse and how, so as to give input in the right places. In recent work, Vervliet addressed the concept of bound creativity in the long and groundbreaking discussion about the performance practice of Bach choirs.³⁴ Another deliberate example is the use of grounded theory to analyze discussions on historically informed performance practice in order to create new educational materials.³⁵

This demand for discourse analysis is not necessarily meant as a critique of the use of the term “authenticity”; rather, it acknowledges its use as a fact that needs to be contextualized. Or, to put it in Mieke Bal’s terms, in order to understand and preempt future developments of the field we need to follow the travel of the concept of “authenticity” or “historical information,”³⁶ that, notwithstanding its deconstruction, had some remarkable stopovers in recent years in many formerly “foreign” territories.³⁷

Performance as experiment

The concept of performance as experiment – beyond the laboratory – although already well-known in practice-led research, seems to me not yet to have been fully explored in early music studies. Relating to the natural sciences, Rheinberger defined experiments as hybrid, impure, as non-determinable and as generators of surprises.³⁸ According to Stallschus’ article,³⁹ Rheinberger used the metaphor of the spiderweb in order to explain the nature of an experiment: experiments are arrangements in which we are able to catch something, though we do not know exactly what that something is or even when it will occur. This reminded me very much of Bruce Hayne’s chapter on serendipity, saying that simply by

34. Vervliet, S. & Van Looy, B. (2010). “Bach’s Chorus Revisited: Historically Informed Performance Practice as ‘Bounded Creativity’”. *Early Music*, 38(2), 205-213. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/i40033173>

35. Mateos-Moreno, D. & Alcaraz-Iborra, M. (2013). “Grounded Theory as a Methodology to Design Teaching Strategies for Historically Informed Musical Performance.” *Music Education Research*, 15(2), 231-248.

36. Bal, M. *Travelling Concepts in the Humanities. A Rough Guide*. University of Toronto Press.

37. Tarling, J. (2012). Historically Informed Gardening. Part I. *Musica Antiqua. UK Quarterly Early Music Magazine*, 2012(1) http://musicaantiqua.co.uk/Images/Issue_1/Articles/Judy%20Tarling%20article.pdf; http://musicaantiqua.co.uk/Images/Issue_2/Articles/Judy_Tarling_Historical_Gardening_partII.pdf (2012/2); http://musicaantiqua.co.uk/Images/Issue_3/MA3_Judy.pdf (2021/3), and more recently Tarling, J., *Landscapes of Eloquence? Finding Rhetoric in the English Landscape Garden*, <https://www.judytarling.com/gardens-of-eloquence>.

38. Rheinberger, H.-J. (1977). *Toward a History of Epistemic Things: Synthesizing Proteins in the Test Tube*. Stanford University Press.

39. Stallschus, S. (2013). “A Theory of Experimentation in Art? Reading Kubler’s History of Art after Rheinberger’s Experimental Systems.” In M. Schwab (Ed.). *Experimental Systems. Future Knowledge in Artistic Research*. (pp. 15-25). Leuven University Press.

experimenting with performance practices we might, by accident, achieve a sound that existed in the past, but since we do not know how the past sounded, we won't realize it.⁴⁰

“Authentic” performers prevailing vs. reception as part of the art

Following the deconstructions of authenticity in early music in the 1980s in Euro-American research, Dulak described a “less ideological, more self-critical, and increasingly tolerant” atmosphere of the early music movement “both of unorthodoxy and of forthright expressivity.”⁴¹ According to him, this atmosphere was created exactly because of the deconstruction of the “absolutely authentic” in historic performance, because of the insight, that “the performer remains ‘authentically’ twentieth century no matter how thoroughly ‘historically informed’ he or she is.”

This focus on the performer seems to have been another golden way out of the loss of a holistic “authenticity”: if the sound-product cannot be original, then let it be the performers themselves, even if their “authenticity” is admittedly contemporary. With the historically informed “authentic” performer, early music reception, production, and event collapse into concepts of music practices and embodied knowledge.

The black box of the historically informed performer was meant to lead the way out of the originality dilemma of the movements. Nevertheless, to put the concept of “authenticity” into the performer might have triggered a kind of liberation from the so-called Baroque police, but was anything but a conceptual way out of the “authenticity” dilemma. Although embodied knowledges and their reenactments are looked upon as counter concepts of academic knowledge (in the sense of practices as situated answers to questions about artistic methods), on another level of reflection they lead into a theoretical no man's land:

A first hint of this can be seen in the fact that “authenticity” of the performer is by no means an early music concept: radio programs as well as concert and CD reviews relate “authenticity” to music performers of all genres, with quite a variety of meanings attached to the term.⁴²

In 2003, Dagmar Hoffmann-Axthelm published a psychologically based approach to the notion of the authentic performer. She characterized the authentic artist as having direct

40. Haynes, B. (2007). p. 7.

41. Dulak, M. (1993). p. 32: “less ideological, more self-critical, and increasingly tolerant” atmosphere of the Early Music movement “both of unorthodoxy and of forthright expressivity.” “the performer remains ‘authentically’ twentieth century no matter how thoroughly ‘historically informed.’”

42. Bernays, U. (2002, December 19). Die verspielte Authentizität. *Neue Zürcher Zeitung*

<https://www.nzz.ch/article8K4CV-1.447724>; Richter, G. Musik muss authentisch sein, Deutschlandfunk Kultur Profil / Archiv, 13.7.2010; Vratz, C. (2015, December 2). CD-Rezension Sol Gabetta Authentisch.

<https://www.concerti.ch/rezensionen-ch/sol-gabetta-authentisch/> MacNamara, M. (2017, September 5). “The Historically Informed Ego: Young Musicians Take Up the Early Music Challenge.” In *Classical Voice. Concerts, Artists, Critical Reviews* <https://www.sfcv.org/articles/feature/historically-informed-ego-young-musicians-take-early-music-challenge>.

access to his childlike ego, to a realm beyond rationality.⁴³ This bears remarkable traits of the 19th century concept of the genius inhabiting the irrational area of art and, as described by Lachmayer among others, has, as a concept, remarkable links to the conservatoire tradition the movement in its beginnings actually tried to overcome.⁴⁴ The veneration of some composers (foremost Bach) in the HIP movements and of performers (lately e.g. Teodor Currentzis at the beginning of his career or the excitement about countertenors and their voices) can often fall into the same category as the concept of genius.

Seen in this light, the “authentic” performer becomes a non-measurable category of performance reception, that in its individuality excludes all forms of collaboration, since it can be attached only to individuals, not to ensembles, groups or orchestras, or multifold authorships. Donna Haraway’s notion of academic knowledge as playing the God trick by claiming to operate beyond perspective and adhering to the realm of the absolute seems to enter through the back door in the notion of the “authentic performer” as genius.⁴⁵ In Kaleva’s analysis of early modern Italian recitative as artistic practice, exactly this determinist core of the notion of the artist’s authenticity comes to the fore.⁴⁶ Setting out to unite historical and empirical epistemologies, he operates at the core of what is at stake in the early music movements. His qualitative analyses that employ iterative loops of feedback and critique, are based on historical criteria. Nevertheless, his conclusion seems to deconstruct his own undertaking: “The significance of this type of both research-led practice and practice-led research is vital in modern early music because it presents a conjunction between reason and intuition and historical and personal authenticity.”⁴⁷ The magic term again, holding up the oppositional construction of a traditional rational and a “new” incorporated knowledge, that does not resolve their inherent paradoxes.

I do not think that, on a theoretical level, one can still adhere to the notion of two opposed camps in the discussions about early music, like scholars such as Gjerdingen described it:

“The catchphrase ‘historically informed’ can be incendiary in the world of Western classical music. To its proponents it means performing music of the past on instruments of the past [...] and in the styles of the past [...]. To its opponents it connotes a deceptive marketing ploy that pretends to recover the irrecoverable sounds and manners of musicians who died

43. Hoffmann-Axthelm, D. (2003). 'Aus der Seele' oder 'wie ein abgerichteter Vogel'? Versuch über künstlerische Authentizität. *Alte Musik zwischen Geschichte und Geschäft*. (Basler Jahrbuch für historische Musikpraxis 27) (pp. 35-44). Amadeus.

44. Lachmayer, H. (2010). "Staging" Knowledge. Inszenierung von Wissensräumen als künstlerisch-wissenschaftliche Forschungspraxis. In G. Bast & Felderer, B. (Ed.) *Art and Now. Über die Zukunft künstlerischer Produktivitätsstrategien*. (p. 61-78). Springer.

45. Haraway, D. (1988). "Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective." *Feminist Studies*. 14(3), 575-599.

46. Kaleva, D. (2014). "Performative Research: A Performance-led Study of 'Lamento d'Arianna' with Historically Informed Rhetorical Gesture." *Musicology Australia*. 36(2), 209-234.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/08145857.2014.958273>

47. Kaleva, D. (2014), 231.

before the dawn of recording.”⁴⁸ As we have seen, both of these attitudes – when theoretically deconstructed – collapse into their opposites, the very concepts against which they were trying to unfold subversive powers.

More recent theories about the concepts of “Remix”⁴⁹ and “Preenactment”⁵⁰ completely deny the possibility of originality but characterize the performative event as always bearing traits of the past and always shaping the future in its adaptations and its social impact.

The real subversive power for a redefinition of the movement formerly called historically informed in the light of artistic research therefore seems to me not to lie in the demand for “another kind of knowledge” or “another kind of gaining knowledge” – they are there already –, but in the acceptance and conscious contextualization of a diversity of methods we need to use in order to establish notions of past musics and sounds: we need to acknowledge the diverse ways of gaining knowledge about them and accept these as always contributing to the sounds of present day performances as well.

Accepting this open-ended notion of performance as experiment might lead the way out of another heavily researched dilemma of the early music movements: out of the problem of the impossibility of a period audience. Until now, this has resulted in thoughts about how we can make unknown past music relevant for audiences.⁵¹ A step not yet undertaken by early music research thoroughly, is the one into the area of music psychology and questions of how to intellectually and emotionally manipulate audiences in order to embrace unknown past repertoires. Crispin’s reflections about a co-creativity of audiences who partner with performers and composers rather than remain in a pleasurable but intellectually disengaged passivity explores the yet unknown realms of the possibilities of historical manipulation of audiences and centers the focus away from the performer onto the performative system as a whole, including time and space.⁵² The subversive potential of the early music movements today lies in experimenting with the classical concert setting along these lines.

48. Gjerdingen, R. O. (2014). “‘Historically Informed’ Corpus Studies.” *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*. 31(3), 192-204, here p. 192. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2014.31.3.192>

49. See above, fn. 21, 22.

50. Marchart, O. (2019). Zeitschleifen. Politisch-theoretische Überlegungen zu Preenactments und realen Utopien. In A. Czirak, S. Nikoleit, F. Oberkrome, V. Straub, R. Walter-Jochum & M. Wetzels (Eds.). *Performance zwischen den Zeiten. Reenactments und Preenactments in Kunst und Wissenschaft* (pp. 129-139). transcript. <https://doi.org/10.14361/9783839446027>.

51. Risi, C. (2014). “Baroque Opera Today: An Essay on the Concept of Historically Informed Performance Practice.” In S. Döhring & S. Rauch (Eds.). *Musiktheater im Fokus. Gedenkschrift für Heinz Becker*. (pp. 387-393). Studio-Verlag. See also Kelber, M. (2018). Vom ‘Period Ear’ zum ‘Period Body’: Zur Hörerfahrung von Tänzerinnen und Tänzern um 1500. M. Zorn & U. Lenker (Eds.). *(Zu-)hören interdisziplinär*. Allitera. https://epub.ub.uni-muenchen.de/69894/1/MVM_Zuhoeren_Kelber.pdf

52. Crispin, D. M. (2013). “Of Arnold Schoenberg’s Klavierstück op. 33a, ‘a Game of Chess,’ and the Emergence of New Epistemic Things.” In M. Schwab (Ed.). *Experimental Systems. Future Knowledge in Artistic Research*. (pp. 15-25). Leuven University Press.

Temporal exoticism

As a last item on my incomplete and subjective list of possible features of HIP beyond authenticity, I would like to bring to the fore Upton's publication on the similarity of concepts of authenticity in early and pop music:

To some extent, musical revivals of pre-Classical music function as a kind of temporal exoticism, exchanging imaginative travel in time, for travel in space in the minds of listeners.⁵³

At another place in her text, Upton speaks about early music that is not "authentic" to the past, but yet another "modern medievalism." Both notions are not at all new to the discussions surrounding the movements formerly called historically informed – although they might not have been called that way; what is new is how she contextualizes them. She deconstructs Taruskin's notion of modernism in early music as discriminatory by excluding the pop-cultural and folk-music contexts in which many early music performers grew up. And the folk music scene discusses "authenticity" in ways comparable to discussions of the early music movements.⁵⁴ So practice-led research into early music should consider crossing genre borders more often in the direction of the popular and the traditional in order to make the contemporary visible, hearable, and acceptable in early music performances.

Perhaps this new bridge into popular music could even help in defining new unique features of early music beyond authenticities: on the one hand this could happen via concepts of collaborative authorship comparable to those in popular, folk, and traditional musics; on the other hand, by bringing into focus musicking practices beyond the written, whose improvisational features are yet another common characteristic of popular and early musics. The resemblances between the two fields seem to be even clearer than is the case with applications of historically informed performance practice to classic and Romantic repertoires. The focus on improvisational techniques of creating performances might even presuppose a different – and perhaps younger – audience, one more willing to be surprised, and that can once again make the live performance the event again it deservedly was before the Corona pandemic. Accordingly, it is precisely in the unique distance from the so-called authentic and with the integration of other genres that a new unique selling point may emerge: the improvisatory and the collaborative as a historical practice of performing, embodying, and hearing. In the best case, this also dissolves traditional role distributions in the research and performance process with a conception of early music that transcends not only historical time and space, but also prescribed roles in performance participation.

53. Upton, E. (2012). "Concepts of Authenticity in Early Music and Popular Music Communities." *Ethnomusicology Review*. 17. <https://ethnomusicologyreview.ucla.edu/printpdf/journal/volume/17/piece/591>

54. See e.g. Hagmann, L., Morrissey, F. A. (2019). "Multiple Authenticities in Folksong." In T. Claviez, B. Sweers & K. Imesch Oechlin (Eds.). *Theory and Practice of Authenticity in Global Cultural Production*. Vernon Press forthcoming and the research project with the same title https://www.cgs.unibe.ch/forschung/drittmittelprojekte/authenticity/index_ger.html.

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